

Study of LiCoO₂+C₆₀ hybrid cathode using neutron and ion-beam profiling methods

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Abstract

Thin films of a hybrid cathode designed for all-solid-state Li-ion batteries (ASSLIBs), based on a combination of LiCoO₂ (LCO) and C₆₀ phases, were prepared by simultaneous ion beam sputtering of LiCoO₂ and thermal evaporation of C₆₀. The sub-micrometer-thick films were analyzed using the Neutron Depth Profiling (NDP) and Rutherford Back Scattering (RBS) methods (in the Center of Accelerator and Nuclear Analytical Methods – NPI CANAM infrastructure) to measure the depth distribution of lithium, cobalt, and other building elements. Both NDP and RBS analytical methods used provided essential information about the profiling of elements in the hybrid layer and showed the influence of the fullerene phase and the charge collector metal on their distribution. It was confirmed that the presence of C₆₀ leads to the higher accumulation of Li on the surface and their slight but broad decrease below the surface. Uneven distribution was also observed for Co, C and O. After depositing the top current collector, a significant decrease in Li and changes in concentrations of other elements occurred in the surface region. It is assumed that the uneven distributions of structural elements in the hybrid LCO+C₆₀ mixtures are due to the difference in electrochemical potentials of the deposited elements.

Introduction

With the technological advancement of modern society, the study of materials for energy storage systems and related techniques has a tremendous impact on the scientific sector [Sikarwar & Sharma 2024]. In recent years, a suitable alternative to lithium-ion batteries (LIBs) has been sought, with several excellent candidates coming into consideration, in particular, sodium and lithium-sulfur batteries [Lin et al. 2022], but even today LIBs are the most widely used and commercially explored battery cells. Lithium transition metal oxides such as LiCoO₂ (LCO) are functional intercalation compounds suitable for use in rechargeable LIBs. It is currently a well-approved material for battery cathodes mainly due to the high mobility of lithium ions. LiCoO₂ has a theoretical gravimetric capacity of 273 mAh/gr and consists of a layered framework [Paulsen et al. 2000]. The cobalt atoms are in trivalent oxidation state (Co³⁺) and are located between two layers of oxygen atoms (O²⁻), meanwhile the Co³⁺ cations occupy alternating planes (111) along a single axis (111) defined by a small distortion of the trigonal symmetry, and the Li⁺ cations occupy octahedral sites in the 2D planes between the anionic CoO₂ layers. The OCV (Open Circuit Voltage) of 3.5-4.5 V for Li/Li_xCoO₂ combination corresponds to the oxidation potentials of Co⁴⁺/Co³⁺. The high mobility of lithium ions is related to the spacing of the oxygen layers from the lithium layers, and the high electron affinity of the low-spin Co(IV)/Co(III) pair, which makes the oxygen layers highly polarizable with respect to the cobalt layers.

The properties of LCO as a cathode strongly depend on the specific physical properties such as porosity and the size of the particles in the film. This is especially true at the mesoscopic scale, where the dimensions affect the macroscopic properties of the materials. So far, however, because of technical difficulties [Sun et al. 2024] it has not been possible to fully exploit the gravimetric capacity of the LCO. For this it would be necessary to extend the potential range, but at higher voltages a phase transition from hexagonal to monoclinic phase occurs, causing structural damage to the electrodes [Xiang et al. 2020]. In addition, also electrolyte decomposition and Co dissolution appear, which contributes significantly to the rapid loss of the battery capacitance.

During our study of this material, we proposed following the others [Guo et al. 2024, Jiang et al. 2021] to use fullerene buckyballs (C_{60}) in combination with LCO. It is because fullerenes can reduce the internal resistance, increase charge/discharge rate and the overall power density, prevent electrolyte decomposition and minimize undesirable side reactions at high voltage [Hudaya et al. 2015]. In addition, the C_{60} can also work as a thermal stabilizer [Nikonova et al. 2021]. In our previous work [Ceccio et al. 2024] we have studied the effects of doping of LCO with the buckyballs, both in the form of a thin coating and in combination (i.e., mixing) with LCO obtained by co-deposition of both components. Interestingly, a peak at the surface together with a significant reduction of the lithium distribution under the current collector was observed when $LiCoO_2$ was deposited in a mixture with C_{60} . This effect was assigned to the difference in electrochemical potentials between the co-deposited material and a (top) golden current collector. In some of our previous studies was demonstrated that the co-deposition of the transitional metals and fullerenes often leads to self-organization at various micro-to-macro levels [Vacik et al. 2011, Vacik et al. 2001] with a driving force attributed to the immiscibility of the metal and fullerene phases. If there is no pronounced phase separation (e.g., self-organization) developed in the mixture, its microstructure can be formed as separated metal nanoparticles embedded with varying densities depending on the ratio of the deposited phases in fullerene environment, which can be polymerized to varying degrees. For example, in the case of the LCO+ C_{60} mixture, it was found that the LCO particles are randomly distributed in C_{60} , so that the LCO+ C_{60} can be seen as a stack of LCO nanostructures diluted in the C_{60} phase with various structural defects and voids that facilitate the migration of Li ions [Arie & Lee 2010].

This finding prompted us to inspect also other types of metal coatings and to see their effect on the local re-distribution of elements in the C_{60} -based LCO cathodes. Thus, in this work we selected as a current collector thin aluminum layer and analyzed its impact on Li (and other structural elements) redistribution. It should be noted that elemental inhomogeneities in ASSLIBs electrodes prepared with a fullerene phase have so far (due to the electrochemical potentials of current collectors) been investigated using nuclear analytical methods, in fact, only in [Ceccio et al. 2024].

The electrical properties of LIBs / ASSLIBs are based on the electrochemical potentials of their constituents; therefore, their study is usually focused on the closely related parameters such as specific capacitance, potential window or energy and power densities. A number of spectroscopic techniques such as X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy [Wood & Teeter 2018], Raman spectroscopy [Gu et al. 2023] or inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry [Schwieters et al. 2017] are therefore used for ongoing research and development of LIBs and their components. Although these methods are irreplaceable for study of basic properties of LIBs / ASSLIBs, they are not so suitable for analyzing the depth distribution of the structural elements and to monitor behavior of LIBs (or their components) at a microscopic level. Instead, specific nuclear analytical methods can open a view into depth profiling of elements in thin ASSLIBs and surface zones of LIBs, and shed more light on their properties based on events occurring in the microstructure (and possibly reveal still hidden effects). Such methods include non-destructive depth profiling utilizing charged particles and/or thermal neutrons, in

particular Rutherford Backscattering Spectroscopy (RBS) using milli- and/or micro-beams [Morita et al. 2018], and Neutron Depth Profiling (NDP) based on thermal/cold neutrons [Lamaze et al. 2003, Tomandl et al. 2020]. Both methods have the great advantage of allowing repeated non-destructive measurements of structural element concentrations as a function of depth. In the case of high-flux neutron beams, operando NDP can monitored behavior (e.g., change in distribution) of certain elements (e.g., Li) in real time [Vacik et al. 2024].

Aluminum is used as a cathode current collector in LIBs / ASSLIBs due to its low price, high electrochemical stability and conductivity and relatively high corrosion resistance [Gabryelczyk et al. 2021]. From an electrochemical point of view, the reason why Al metal was chosen in this study was significantly different electrochemical potential than the previously used Au collector [Ceccio et al. 2024], with our intention to examine how Al would affect the distribution of Li in the sample.

In LIBs, the standard reduction potential of the current collector (E^0_M) is typically referred to the lithium metal, rather than to the Standard Hydrogen Electrode - SHE (which is declared to be $E^0 = 0V$ at any temperature). The reduction potential of the lithium metal ($Li^+ + e^- \rightarrow Li$) is very low (-3.04 V vs SHE), so we can use it to express the potential of another material relative to it by subtracting the value of the standard potential of lithium ($E^0_{Li/SHE}$). The Al metal exhibits a highly negative standard reduction potential, i.e., $E^0_{Al/SHE} = -1.662$ V (vs. SHE), which is given by the reaction $Al^{3+} + 3e^- \rightarrow Al$, while relative to Li ($E^0_{Li/SHE} = -3.04$ V) is: $E^0_{Al/Li} = E^0_{Al/SHE} - E^0_{Li/SHE} = +1.38$ V. For comparison, in our previous work with the Au current collector: $E^0_{Au/Li} = +4.54$ V (for the oxidation state of Au^{3+}), and in the case of Co: $E^0_{Co/Li} = +2.76$ V.

Because of the large differences in $E^0_{M/Li}$, one can assume that the distribution of Li in the LCO+C₆₀ mixture encompassed with an Al coatings should be affected, and with even relatively small changes observable by NDP. Moreover, since the relative atomic weight of Al (26.9815) is much smaller than that of Co (58.933195), it will be possible to use also RBS and analyze the distribution of Co (and the other structural elements) in thin LCO+C₆₀ even with an Al collector on the surface (this would not be possible for the sample with the Au collector, because the superposition of signals from Au and Co in the RBS spectra would make the evaluation difficult).

The main objective of this paper is to perform a similar experiment as in our previous study [Ceccio et al. 2024], but with Al as the (bottom and top) current collectors, and to determine whether (and how) the much smaller electrochemical potential of Al ($E^0_{Al/Li} = +1.38$ V) than Au ($E^0_{Au/Li} = +4.54$ V) would affect the Li distribution in the LCO+C₆₀ layer. If the Li distribution were to change and be different from that observed in [Ceccio et al. 2024], then it would be confirmed that metals with different electrochemical properties used as current collectors affect the Li distribution in ASSLIBs comprising C₆₀ hybrid component. The aim was also to clarify whether the distribution of the main protagonists (Li and Co) in the hybrid layer is somehow related.

Materials and methods

For the experiment, we prepared a series of thin film mixtures by co-depositing LCO and C₆₀ (see Fig. 1) onto Si(110) wafers and microscope cover slides (see Tab. 1) in high vacuum conditions (2×10^{-6} mbar). LCO was deposited onto the substrates using a method of ion beam sputtering performed at the Low Energy Ion Facility (LEIF) assembled in the NPI CANAM (Center of Accelerators and Nuclear Analytical Methods) infrastructure [<http://www.ujf.cas.cz/en/research-development/large-research-infrastructure-and-centres/canam/>]. For sample preparation, the LEIF was operated with a 20 keV Ar⁺

ion beam focused onto the surface of the LCO target (2 x 0.125 in., 99.9%, MTI Corp.) mounted on an Al target holder with a shape of a 6-faces polyhedron inclined with an active face having attached LCO at 45° (upward) to the incident ion beam. The target was placed face-to-face with the substrates at approx. 100 mm. A lab-made evaporator (a graphite crucible with a W resistance wire), installed below the substrate holder at a distance of 100 mm, served as a source for C₆₀ (99.9% purity, Nanograph). The evaporator temperature was controlled using a thermocouple (a K-type wire sonde) inserted into the crucible. The evaporation process was maintained at 450 °C. A manual shutter was used during the calibration of the ion beam and the adjustment of the crucible heating, to prevent unwanted deposition on the substrates. The same experimental setup was used in LEIF also in the preparation of the Al current collector using a high-purity Al target (50 mm x 1 mm, 99.99%, Porex sro) mounted on one of the free faces of the target holder.

Fig. 1: Schematic view of the preparation of hybrid layers formed by the simultaneous deposition of fullerenes (by thermal evaporation of C₆₀) and LiCoO₂ (using ion sputtering of the LCO target).

Tab. 1. A list of the samples and their parameters (thickness was obtained by simulation of the NDP and RBS data)

SAMPLE	number	substrate	thickness (10 ¹⁵ cm ⁻²)	size (mm)
LCO+C ₆₀ /Al	2	microscope cover slides	2400	10 x 10
		Si	2400	15 x 15
Al/LCO+C ₆₀ /Al	2	microscope cover slides	3600	10 x 10
		Si	3600	15 x 15

The deposited samples were analyzed by the NDP method [Hnatowicz et al. 2010] at the LVR-15 research reactor operated by the Research Center Rez [www.cvrez.cz/en]. To briefly recall, the NDP is a specific analytical tool for noninvasive investigating of depth profiles of several technologically important light elements (e.g., He, Li, B, S), particularly lithium, actually ⁶Li with a natural abundance of 7.8% in solids. The depth resolution of the method is nominally up to 10 nm, which allows monitoring even small changes in the depth distribution of the relevant elements (for Li, such changes

may occur in LIBs / ASSLIBs during the lithiation/delithiation processes, but the changes can also be found in the individual battery components [Tomandl et al. 2023, Cannavò et al. 2023]).

In general, the NDP method established in the NPI CANAM infrastructure [www.ujf.cas.cz/en/] is based on the intense exoenergetic nuclear reactions of thermal neutrons with specific isotopes of certain elements, namely the neutron-induced reactions with the isotropic emission of charged particles with characteristic energies (in a keV-MeV range). In the case of ${}^6\text{Li}$, the nuclear reaction (n_{th},α) has a high cross section of 940 b and an energy reaction of 4.782 MeV, and is as follows:

The NDP measurements in this work were performed in a vacuum chamber (of a 10^{-1} mbar background pressure) with $\sim 90 \mu\text{m}$ thin entrance and exit Al-based flanges installed in the chamber to reduce the unwanted radiation background due to the parasitic reactions induced in the flanges by passing neutrons. Since the neutron beam coming from a horizontally set neutronguide has the shape of a narrow-elongated slit (approx. 10 mm high, 8 cm wide), the flat samples were fixed on a thin plastic frame (prepared by a 3D printer) and irradiated at an inclined angle of 5° to avoid a possible self-shielding of neutrons on the substrates. A flux of the neutron beam at the LVR-15 reactor power maintained at around 10 MW was about $7 \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ and its Cd ratio indicating quality of thermalization of the reactor beam was measured to be $\sim 10^4$. A fully depleted PIPS detector (50 mm², Canberra) with standard electronics (and a Triumph MCA) was used to detect the emitted charged particles and measure their energy spectra.

By analyzing the residual energies and counting rates of the emitted particles in each channel, the concentration of elements at different depths of the material can be determined (as charged particles pass through the sample, they lose their energy and the residual parts indicate the depths at which the particles emission sites were located). To obtain the Li depth distribution, a commercially available SIMNRA code for simulation of nuclear reaction analysis [http://mam.home.ipp.mpg.de] was applied in evaluation of the ${}^6\text{Li}$ -NDP energy spectra. For this purpose, it was to measure the standards (e.g., $1.1 \mu\text{m } {}^6\text{LiF}$) under the same experimental conditions, i.e., the same experimental setup with the identical detector-sample solid angle and the same neutron fluence, to determine the input setup parameters for the simulations of the spectra.

To determine the depth distribution of other elements constituting the LCO+C₆₀ mixture, RBS measurements were performed. The aim was to determine whether the non-uniform lithium depth profile results in a reverse non-uniform cobalt (and other structural elements) distribution that would allow compensation for the defect in layer density caused by lithium migration. The study was carried out at the Tandetron MC 4130 accelerator of the NPI CANAM infrastructure. In the experiment, He⁺ ions with an energy of 2 MeV and a low current of about 100 nA were used to avoid radiation radiation damage to the sensitive hybrid structure. It can be mentioned that the RBS method is also used for Li profiling, but a different probe beam is needed, e.g., 9 MeV O⁴⁺ [Morita et al. 2018], which could lead to destructive effects in the sample. The backscattered particles were detected using the partially-depleted ORTEC ULTRA detector with an active area of 50 mm² and a 300 μm thick depletion layer. The detector was positioned at a backscatter angle of 170° in accordance with the Cornell geometry. For RBS, glass (microscope slides) was used, which, as an amorphous material, allowed to avoid channeling of the probing particles during the measurements. Like the NDP spectra, the RBS data were also processed using the SIMNRA code.

As mentioned above, the SIMNRA code allows Li profiling based on the spectra measured by the NDP, but it does not allow obtaining profiles of other elements in the sample that do not generate charged

particles in reactions with thermal neutrons. Similarly, for the selected experimental setup with 2 MeV alpha beam it was not possible to obtain Li profiles using RBS, as the upper edge of the Li spectrum is around 150 keV, which is however in the high background area. Therefore, it was advisable to perform measurements by both NDP and RBS methods and analyze the spectra using the SIMNRA code so that the Li profile obtained by simulating the NDP data is processed using also information about the stoichiometric ratios of Co, C and O obtained by RBS, and vice versa.

In general, it should be noted that NDP and RBS analyses are burdened with errors resulting from various experimental inaccuracies, e.g., in NDP when determining the precise 3D geometry between the sample and the detector, in the homogeneity of neutron beam irradiation, in determining the neutron fluence, etc., similarly in RBS when determining the exact energy and geometry of the setup, in both methods when determining the energy calibration and energy resolution and especially when determining the quality of samples with respect to their surface roughness and porosity. The measurement is also affected by background radiation and electronics errors (pile-up, dead time, charging). All of the aforementioned experimental inaccuracies introduce errors into the data evaluation, so it is necessary to state that both methods are burdened with errors that can be roughly estimated in the order of several percent (which only applies to high measurement statistics).

Results

Fig. 2 shows: (a) an alpha peak from the ${}^6\text{Li}(n,\alpha)t$ reaction obtained in the NDP measurements of a thin LCO+C₆₀ mixture co-deposited on the Si substrate (without a top Al current collector), and (b) results of the profile simulation (by SIMNRA) of all structural elements of ASSLIB (Li, Co, C and O), and (c) details of the simulation in the first $+150 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ depth. Since the sample was prepared without a top coating, the right edge of the spectrum (a) corresponds to the energy position of alpha particles emitted from the sample surface with a nominal (lossless) energy of 2055 keV. As can be seen (a), the measured counting rate of alpha particles is uneven for different energies, which is due to the non-uniform distribution of the parent nuclei (${}^6\text{Li}$) in the sample. The dominant peak at the surface contains about 13% of the total Li atoms (N_{tot}) in the sample but is concentrated in less than 10% of the sample volume (V_{tot}) and is followed by a decline, corresponding to $0.2 N_{\text{tot}} / 0.24 V_{\text{tot}}$, towards the bulk of the layer. From about halfway through the thickness, the alpha spectrum remains then uniform (with $0.67 N_{\text{tot}} / 0.66 V_{\text{tot}}$).

This specific phenomenon was also observed in our previous study [Ceccio et al. 2024], where, however, the LCO+C₆₀ mixture was coated with a thin layer of gold as the top current collector. In this work, Li accumulation on the LCO+C₆₀ surface is observed without a charged collector. This suggests that the metal films on the LCO+C₆₀ surface are not the primary cause of the non-uniform Li distribution. However, as already observed in [Ceccio et al. 2024], metal coatings can still affect the Li profiling in the hybrid layers due to their different chemical potential and applied voltage.

The simulation in Fig. 2b, c shows the conversion of the energy spectrum to the depth dependence of the relative concentration for Li and other structural elements (the depth is given in the units of 10^{15} cm^{-2}). Fig. 2b demonstrates the profiling over the entire thickness of the hybrid layer, Fig. 2c only the narrow part near the surface. The simulations confirm that the structural elements are distributed unevenly, especially Li with a high peak ($\sim 50\%$ of the relative concentration) around the surface ($0 - 50 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), and a broad decrease ($\sim 9\%$) below ($50 - 400 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), following with a relatively stable distribution (about 12%) extending up to the interface with the bottom Al collector (where a small amount $< 5\%$ was also indicated). Interestingly, concentration of Co on the surface was found very low ($\sim 10\%$), following with a narrow peak ($\sim 35\%$) just in a location of the Li decrease (ca $50 - 100$

$\times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), then in the remaining depth (ca $100 - 1800 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$) its distribution is stable ($\sim 22\%$). In the case of O and C, their relative concentrations adjust to the variations in the Li and Co concentrations. A decrease ($\sim 24\%$) in O is evident at the surface ($0 - 50 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), which is then stably distributed (over approximately 50%) in the remaining layer thickness. Interestingly, C (C_{60}) shows only slight fluctuations, around 15%, up to the bottom collector, where its concentration increases to 35% (it is due to the exposure of Al to C_{60} before stabilizing the ion beam for sputtering of LCO).

Discussing the NDP data, it should be noted that only spectra from the interaction of neutrons with $\text{Li}({}^6\text{Li})$ are used, since the interaction with other structural elements do not generate charged particles. However, to successfully complete the simulation, it is needed to estimate and optimize their relative concentrations for all structural elements.

Fig. 2: a) NDP spectrum with an optimized simulation (by SIMNRA) of the $\{\text{LiCoO}_2 + \text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{Si}_{\text{substrate}}\}$ thin hybrid film with a single bottom current collector (only alpha part of the spectrum was analyzed; energy of $\alpha_{\text{edge}} \rightarrow 2055 \text{ keV}$, energy per channel $\rightarrow 2.72 \text{ keV/ch}$), b) evaluated depth profiles of structural elements (their relative concentration vers depth in at. 10^{15} per cm^2), c) details of the profiles in the subsurface layer ($0 - 150 \times 10^{15}$ at. cm^{-2}).

The requirement to determine the depth distribution of Co, C and O in LCO+C₆₀ can be addressed by the RBS method. However, this method allows, in this particular case, less-intrusive profiling only for Co; for lighter elements (Li, C and O), the spectrum is slightly obscured by the back-scattering of the alpha probe particles from the elements of the glass substrate (Si, Na, Ca, Te, O). To evaluate the RBS spectra, it is therefore necessary to first measure the substrate and apply the obtained data in simulation of the real spectrum with a hybrid layer (and current collector) deposited on glass, i.e., {LCO+C₆₀ / Al / glass}. It was done in the following.

Fig. 3 demonstrates: a) the raw RBS spectrum, (b) the simulation (depth profiles) of the entire spectrum, and (c) the simulation from the near-surface region only (0 – 200 x 10¹⁵ at. cm⁻²). The profiling of Co could be determined with fairly good accuracy (the presence of Te is only slight), however, the substrate elements had to be taken into account in the case of C and O, and the Li profile, which is not recorded in the RBS spectrum (because of a very low backscattered energy of the probing alpha particles), was obtained by optimized simulation.

The evaluation of the RBS spectrum showed that, similar to NDP, the distribution of elements in the hybrid layer is uneven, with the course of the Co and Li profiles largely repeating: Li accumulates on the surface (0 – 50 x 10¹⁵ at. cm⁻²), which subsequently falls into a shallow (ca 9%) but wide (50 – 500 x 10¹⁵ at. cm⁻²) pit, after which the course becomes uniform (ca 12%) up to the current collector interface; similarly, Co is strongly suppressed in the narrow surface layer, but in the following subsurface part (50 – 100 x 10¹⁵ at. cm⁻²), it shows a peak (35%), followed again by a more or less uniform distribution (23%) up to the Al collector, similar to Li. The O and C curves are very similar to those recorded in simulation of the NDP spectrum.

Fig. 3: a) RBS spectrum (using 2 MeV α -probe, energy per channel was 2.72 keV/ch) and optimized simulation (by SIMNRA) of the $\{\text{LiCoO}_2+\text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{glass}\}$ thin hybrid film with a single bottom current collector, b) evaluated depth profiles of structural elements (their relative concentration vers depth in at. 10^{15} per cm^2), c) details of the profile in the subsurface layer (0 – 200 $\times 10^{15}$ at. cm^{-2}).

In the next part of the study, hybrid systems of the same type were prepared, but with a thin Al current collector deposited also on the surface, i.e., thin hybrid systems $\{\text{Al} / \text{LCO}+\text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{Si}\}$ for the NDP and $\{\text{Al} / \text{LCO}+\text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{glass}\}$ for the RBS analyses. The preparation was carried out under the same conditions as for the first hybrid samples.

Fig. 4: a) NDP spectrum and optimal simulation (by SIMNRA) of the $\{\text{Al} / \text{LiCoO}_2+\text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{Si}_{\text{substrate}}\}$ thin hybrid film with top and bottom current collectors (only alpha part of the spectrum was analyzed; energy of $\alpha_{\text{edge}} \rightarrow 2055 \text{ keV}$, energy per channel $\rightarrow 2.72 \text{ keV/ch}$), b) evaluated depth profiles of structural elements (their relative concentration vers depth in at. 10^{15} per cm^2).

Fig. 4a shows the NDP spectrum of the $\{\text{Al} / \text{LCO}+\text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{Si}_{\text{substrate}}\}$ sample, depicting the alpha part of the ${}^6\text{Li}(n, \alpha)t$ reaction in the same energy window as for the $\{\text{LCO}+\text{C}_{60} / \text{Al} / \text{Si}_{\text{substrate}}\}$ layer prepared with only the bottom Al current collector, see Fig. 2a. When comparing these two spectra, several

differences can be seen right away: in this current spectrum (Fig. 4a) the surface peak that was observed in Fig. 2a is missing, instead a relatively shallow but broad dip in the subsurface layer is visible corresponding to about 5% of the sample volume ($V_{\text{tot}} = 0.05$), and 4.5% of Li in the sample ($N_{\text{tot}} = 0.045$); due to the surface current collector, the position of the alpha peak edges has changed – the surface edge has down-shifted by about 5 channels. Fig. 4b shows the depth profiles obtained by simulating the energy spectrum and optimizing the depth distribution of individual structural elements. As can be seen, the Co copies the Li profile, but at a slightly higher concentration level: at the interface with the top current collector (with a width of $120 \times 10^{15} \text{ at. cm}^{-2}$) the relative concentration is 17% and 18% for Li and Co, respectively, then follows (for $450 \times 10^{15} \text{ at. cm}^{-2}$) a slight decrease 12% for Li and 13% for Co, and then a slight increase again 15% for Li and 16% for Co, which extends (for $1650 \times 10^{15} \text{ at. cm}^{-2}$) to the bottom current collector, where a gradual decrease in concentration is observed for both elements. For O, its profile starts at the level of 50% right from the Al surface, and further increases to 52-55% (for $1650 \times 10^{15} \text{ at. cm}^{-2}$) and reaches 65% in the range of the bottom current collector. Carbon starts the profile at the level of 20% just below the top Al layer and remains for a depth of $2600 \times 10^{15} \text{ at. cm}^{-2}$, but then increases to about 30% on the bottom current collector.

Fig. 5a demonstrates the RBS spectrum corresponding to the hybrid system {Al / LCO+C₆₀ / Al / glass} with top and bottom current collectors. The spectrum shows the contribution of the substrate (glass), containing a strong Te impurity (see the peak around the channel 625). Fig. 5b represents the depth profiles of the structural elements of the hybrid layer (the profiles of the substrate elements are not shown). As already mentioned above, to determine the depth profiles of the structural elements it was necessary to subtract the contributions of the elements from the substrate, which is not always possible without errors, and for Li, whose signal does not appear in the RBS spectrum, it was necessary to perform a multi-step simulation, allowing to optimize the simulation curve, which ultimately led to the above satisfactory result.

As can be seen, the depth profiles of the structural elements of the hybrid layer are more fragmented (except for Co) than was the case in the NDP measurements. Surprisingly, the level of Li and Co concentrations is higher (about 5%) than as determined in NDP. One can probably assume that the reason might be the already mentioned disturbances of the RBS signals from the substrate elements, which complicate the evaluation.

Fig. 5: a) RBS spectrum (using 2 MeV α -probe, energy per channel was 2.72 keV/ch) and optimized simulation (by SIMNRA) of the {Al / LiCoO₂+C₆₀ / Al / glass} thin hybrid film with top and bottom current collectors, b) evaluated depth profiles of structural elements (their relative concentration vers depth in at. 10¹⁵ per cm²).

Importantly, the decrease in the relative concentration of Li and Co, observed in the subsurface layer ($\sim 250 \times 10^{15} - 750 \times 10^{15}$ at. cm⁻²) in the NDP measurement was not detected in the simulation of this RBS measurement. One can see that the Co profile is relatively stable up to a depth of 2400×10^{15} at. cm⁻², where its gradual decrease begins and ends at the interface with the bottom current collector. The same applies to Li, whose depth profile shows slight steps, but in most places follows Co. The other two elements O and C have unstable course of the profiles that gradually rising upwards, with O reaching up to 60% in the bottom current collector, and C half the value (30%) in this region.

In essence, it can be stated that the results of both measurements are in very good agreement: NDP provided real distribution of Li and simulated distribution of the other structural elements (Co, O and C); RBS, on the other hand, allowed us to determine the real distribution of Co (and also O and C, whose profiles are, however, complicated by the interference from the substrate's elements), while the Li distribution resulted from the optimized simulation **of the spectrum**. An important part concerns the area of the narrow surface and subsurface layers, where both methods confirmed that Li and Co complement each other especially in the case of the hybrid layer with only bottom current collector layer: higher Li accumulation on the surface is accompanied by lower Co presence, lower Li concentration in the subsequent subsurface layer is accompanied by a higher Co concentration. When comparing the simulation results from both methods (Fig. 2b, c and Fig. 3b, c), it is evident that even in the remaining part in depth (up to Al), Li and Co behave the same, their course is more or less stable and uniform (Li: 12%, Co: 23%). So, one can conclude that both elements are somehow interdependent, with a decrease in one element leading to an increase in the other and vice versa. However, it is important to note that, unlike Co, Li is highly mobile and can then as an Li⁺ ion easily migrate in the hybrid system, and respond eventually to the external electric fields. In such a case, the implied connection between these two elements would be disrupted.

The RBS and NDP data obtained in this work have shown us the distribution of structural elements in hybrid LCO+C₆₀ systems with current collectors, but the question is how to explain them. It is known that when certain immiscible elements are combined (co-deposited), spatial separation [Meischein et al. 2022] and even self-organization [Lavrentiev et al. 2005] can occur in some cases. For example, in the case of fullerene and cobalt, a clear phase separation was observed [Lavrentiev et al. 2005] and manifested as separate single crystals of fcc-Co (about 10 nm in size) dispersed in the C₆₀ matrix. One can assume that phase separation can occur similarly in the case of LCO+C₆₀, i.e., where LCO-based nanoparticles with a specific structure dependent on the amount of C₆₀ phase would form and disperse in the fullerene environment, as also shown in [Kaskhedikar & Maier 2009]. The LCO+C₆₀ hybrid mixture has the properties of a strained material due to the weak miscibility of some structural phases (Co and C). However, Li as another element of the system is usually not affected by the phase separation process, but is dramatically influenced by the electrochemical potentials of the environment that control its migration in the system. This is probably the reason for the observed changes in Li distribution in the hybrid layers studied.

Thus, it can be concluded that the changes in the Li distribution observed in this work can be attributed mainly to diffusion induced by electrochemical potential, so that the diffusive nature of lithium is induced by thermal or electrochemical stimuli, which is also the operating principle of LIBs. One possible cause of diffusion can be identified as the oxidation of Co in LCO at the sample surface. Cobalt with a higher oxidation state located at the surface is more prone to generate a higher electrochemical

potential, which would thus affect (direct) the diffusion of lithium towards the depth of the layer. This would create a region of depleted Li, which is exactly the effect observed in this work. And the same effect was observed in our previous work with gold current collectors, which also exhibited a high electrochemical potential compared to Li [Ceccio et al. 2024]. We assume that when the hybrid layer is covered with a thin Al surface layer, this layer acts as a protective barrier that oxidizes instead of cobalt, and the Li distribution remains unchanged or only slightly. Further, it seems that the oxidation of Al also increases the oxidation state of Al itself, but since there are first developed interphase layers between the collector and the LCO, this effect is less influenced and does not cause a significant depletion zone for Li.

Conclusion

In this work, we aimed to demonstrate the possibility to investigate materials for lithium ion batteries using the nuclear profiling methods NDP and RBS. The use of a hybrid deposition setup with ion sputtering and resistive evaporation allowed us to prepare thin hybrid composites (with both LiCoO_2 and C_{60} components) on different substrates.

It turned out that

- the distribution of the structural elements is not homogeneous in the hybrid layer and differs from each other,
- there might be some interdependence between the structural elements, so the distribution of one element affects the distribution of the other,
- the distribution of the elements, especially Li, strongly depends on the top current collector (i.e., on its existence/nonexistence, the type of metal - i.e., its electrochemical parameters -, its thickness, etc.),
- the distribution and migration (diffusion) of Li in $\text{LiCoO}_2+\text{C}_{60}$ is strongly influenced by the electrochemical potential of the structural elements of the system and their distribution,
- the oxidation of structural metal elements may cause a change in their electrochemical potential, which thus affects the diffusion and distribution of Li (and consequently other elements in the hybrid layer).

The desired direction is the application of specific analytical methods that allow non-destructively and repeatedly studying the spatial distribution of individual elements in thin layers of lithium-ion battery materials, which allows monitoring the behavior of batteries at the microscopic level both in-situ and (at high fluxes, especially in the case of neutrons) in operando, i.e., in real time. The knowledge gained can allow a better understanding of the processes that occur at different specific locations in batteries. This can lead faster progress in the development of new types of the LIBS / ASSLIB cells.

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